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IMPACT OF ADVT OF FAIR AND LOVELY ON STUDENT CUSTOMERS IN SATARA

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Fair and Lovely is a well-known brand of HUL, popular among the young generation in cosmetics. The company regularly emphasizes on the advertisement to attract the customer and to survive in changing competition. Earlier, it was a first popular established brand in cosmetics in fairness cream. Now a number of brands Nivea, Fairever, Olay, Vicco, Himani, Ponds etc. are competing with them. Therefore, there is need to assess the ad impact on the customers and to know their perception towards the product.

Design/Methodology/Approach- The present research paper is field survey and based on primary data as well as secondary data. Primary data collected through the instrument schedule and other information availed from the internet. It was executed on 300 students at a college campus. Collected data analyzed with simple statistical tools viz. percentage, mean and standard deviation and presented with tabulation. Two hypotheses were set to test viz. H01: Gender and respondents' opinion are not significantly correlated. H 02: Gender and respondent' perception towards the product features' importance are not significantly correlated.

Findings- Majority respondents were below 25 age, female respondents have a more positive reaction towards ad compare to male, female respondents are more like to purchase offered product in the advertisement. Respondents' television watching frequency is less than 2 hours in a week. Female watching frequency is more compared to male respondents. Respondents felt almost all product features important which are shown in the advertisement. Majority i.e. 76.67% opined that advertisement appeal to them and there is no gender difference in their opinion. They showed their interest to see the ad in near future. The null hypotheses are rejected and alternative hypotheses are accepted as. Gender and respondents' opinion are significantly correlated and gender and perception towards the product features' importance are significantly correlated.

Limitations: The responses collected during 2014-15, responses were nothing but the perception of students, and it may change in future. The result which is obtained in selected area i.e. Satara may not be similar in other metro towns and small cities.

Practical Implications- Paper offer the guidelines to the company to design the ad to tap the rural or small town customer and to decide the frequency of ad to suffice the purpose of advertisement. So that efforts would not be in vein since the customization is the need of today's era.

Originality/Value- Paper comprises with students responses collected from management campus where budding manager students are more conscious of their attire and presentation. In the era of customization and competition, one should keep a close watch on the effects of marketing efforts.

Key Words- Advertisement, Impact, Students Perception, Fair and Lovely

Introduction

India's cosmetics industry estimated at \$950 million and is expected to grow to about \$2.68 billion by 2020. Annual growth of the Indian beauty and cosmetics markets is estimated to remain in the range of 15-20 % in the coming years, twice as fast as that of the US and European markets. Greater awareness in India of the latest global beauty and cosmetics trends are prompting international players to set up their shop in India. Demand for skin whitening products by men as well as women and moisturizers are driving the trend. Over the last five years, cosmetics products have seen a growth of 60%. Companies like Pond's and Fair & Lovely top the list. It observed that Indian rural market offers huge opportunities to the marketers as it is in developing stage and account 80 per cent consumers. The lifestyles of rural consumers have undergone wonderful changes due to growing incomes, increasing literacy rate, exposure TV and interaction with the urban counterpart. Advertisements, especially in television are targeted to a Youth. Youth are bombarded with powerful advertising messages from various media, which are, designed to win their heart. Every business organization is spending a huge amount for this. It is the common perception that many Indian women are partial towards the fairer skin. Recently, noted dermatologists commented that people are now openly asking for a solution to something that has been an obsession through the ages. Equating fairness with beauty has turned out to be a key consumer insight in the case of the fairness creams industry. Hindustan Unilever captures nearly 53% of the market share with Fair & Lovely. Fair & Lovely was first developed and launched in the year 1976. The company has drawn particular scrutiny for its promotions and advertisements featuring darker skinned women turning fairer on using the fairness cream. Hindustan Unilever Limited currently spends about 5-10% of its total marketing budget on digital.

Researcher gone through the various previous literatures and could notice the findings of research as follows

Literature Review

(Lee, 1995) The paper investigates the role of consumers' attitude toward the brand advertising on the accessibility and perceived appropriateness of the brand attributes in their perception of a brand

extension. The effect is examined either for a comparable extension (sneakers from denim clothing) or for a moderately non-comparable extension (perfume/cologne from denim clothing). The result shows that the accessibility of the brand attributes is observed in a similar pattern for both comparable and moderately non-comparable extensions. Advertisement strongly influences consumers' overall attitude toward a brand extension, with the effect being greater for a moderately non-comparable extension than for a comparable extension.

(Soscia, 2009) Study find out that comparative advertising's effect depends on consumers' perceived differentiation among the brands and consumers' level of involvement with the specific product category. Finding demonstrate that high-involvement consumer perceive low differentiation among brands

(Speck, 1998)The study could find out that the perception of advertising clutter is highest in television and direct mail while the highest level of advertising-related communication problems was observed in television and magazines.

(Young, 1986) Results indicate that the effect of music on brand attitude depends on the type and level of involvement. Music had a facilitative effect on brand attitude for subjects in the low involvement condition and a distracting effect for those in the cognitive involvement condition; its effect for those in the affective involvement condition was not clear.

(Weinberg, 1984) The study was undertaken to investigate the perception, attitude, and cognitive response to the advertisement.

(Milesh, 2012) The study tries to measure the effect of some selected FMCG product's television advertisements with commonly used negative emotional appeals on cognitive message processing style of Indian housewives.

(Edwards, 2006) The study could find out that 14% to 24% felt that advertising orthodontists would offer a lower quality of care than non-advertising orthodontists would. Newspaper, magazine, and direct mail advertisements were viewed more favourably than radio, television, and billboard advertisements.

(Chowdhury, 2006) Study find out that three extrinsic cues: brand image, perceived quality, and perceived country of origin have a positive and significant influence on consumers' brand evaluation of beautification brands. Only perceived price has shown no such influence on consumers' brand evaluation.

(Qurat-UJ-Ain Zafar) The study arrived at the conclusion that celebrity endorsements do have an impact on customer's perception and purchase intention.

(Kausar Hayat) Results show that celebrity endorsed advertising is very much eye-catching and influential as compared to non-celebrity endorsements. Celebrity endorsed advertising attributes do affect the purchase intention of consumers. It proves that consumer perception based advertisement & celebrity endorsed advertising positively impact the purchase intention of the consumers.

(Lodhi, 2015) Study find out that advertisements are very useful in creating the awareness among the people but they are failed to build strong perceptions in the mind of consumers. Also, highlight that consumer awareness and consumer perceptions will motivate the consumer to buy a certain product if there is a positive relationship present in between them.

After taking the review from previous literature researcher could find out that there is no any research conducted to assess the student response towards advertisement of Fair and Lovely in Satara as Satara is upcoming in rural market. Thus, efforts made to probe into the situation.

Research Methodology

Fair & Lovely was launched in the year 1976. It is going well with its high market share. It is competing with the brands like Nivea, Fairever, Olay, Vicco, Himani, Ponds etc. Advertisements play a very important role in improving the market share. Hindustan Unilever Limited currently spends about 5-10% of its total marketing budget on digital. Therefore, there is a need to measure the effectiveness of television advertisements on the student customer in Satara with respect to Fair & Lovely of Hindustan Unilever Limited and to know the customer perception towards it.

To suffice the said purpose following objectives are set

1. To assess the ad impact on the customers
2. To know customers perception towards the product

Two hypotheses were set to test viz.

H01: Gender and respondents' opinion are not significantly correlated

H 02 : Gender and respondent' perception towards the product features' importance are not significantly correlated

The study is confined to television advertisements of Fair & Lovely of Hindustan Unilever Limited. Survey conducted at some technical and professional college campus in Satara City. A structured questionnaire was prepared to take the responses of total 300 samples comprises with girl and boy students those are available on the college campus. Only Fair and Lovely users are considered as the sample unit. Collected data analyzed with the help of simple statistical tools such as percentage, mean and hypotheses tested with Pearson mean correlation. The period of study is 2014-2015

Data Analysis

The product Fair & Lovely is consumed by many users and majority of them treat this product of high quality and important for the face. It is also found that majority of these users make its use for fairness than other uses such as sunscreen, dark spots, face clean up, fragrance, etc. as shown in the advertisement. After watching the advertisement and using the product almost half of the respondents recommend it to others for usage.

Findings

Female respondent (56.67%) are more than male respondent 43.33%. Almost (98.33%) respondents are below 25 age. Frequency to see the ad in a weekly in the range of once to five plus in both the gender, not much gender difference in frequency. Majority respondent 76.67% felt advertisement appeal to the customer and here also no gender difference in the opinion. Majority 80% respondents agreed to have a positive reaction towards advertisement and female percentage is more than male ones. Majority 73.33% respondent like to see the ad in future where the female percentage is more than male ones. 72% respondent like to purchase a more offered product where the female percentage is more than male ones. 58% respondent like to share ad to someone where female percentage found more compared to male. Respondents agree with given statement viz. The ad is creative, informative, memorable, original, influential, relevant to the product, reflect company image etc as the mean score is more than 2 and less than 3 with higher deviation. It reveals that respondents are not much conscious to register their opinion towards the perception of the ad. However, they are agreed with the statement that the claims made into ad are believable as the mean score is more than 3. There is no gender difference in the opinion on the said statements.

Collected data does not give the strong opinion on ad message, no uniformity in the respondents opinion towards given statement as just trying to sell the product, a product is of high quality, entice people to try the product, cheaper than the competitors and brand awareness, a company trying to expose itself. As the opinion lies from the 38% to 7.33% and not distinct gender difference in the opinion. 41% respondents watching frequency is less than hour in a day followed by 34% samples watching frequency is 1-2 hours. It reveals that majority of respondents watching frequency is less than 2 hours. Female watching frequency is more than male ones. Respondents felt almost all product features important as the mean score is more than 2 but less than 3. There is no gender difference in the opinion. Male 44% respondents registered their perception, as the ad is memorable and creative whereas 25.88% female felt creative and 11.76% think it is memorable. There is no uniformity in the opinion between both the genders as well within the female respondents have the difference of perception about the advertisement.

Hypotheses Testing

H01: Gender and respondents' opinion are not significantly correlated

Case Summary

Sr.	Opinion	Male			Female			Total		
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
1	Ad is creative	2.64	130	1.086	2.24	170	0.886	2.41	300	0.998
2	Ad is informative	2.91	130	1.245	2.31	170	0.981	2.58	300	1.143
3	Ad is memorable	3.03	130	1.43	2.26	170	0.982	2.6	300	1.258
4	Ad is original	2.92	130	1.346	2.4	170	0.931	2.63	300	1.161
5	Ad is influential	2.82	130	1.283	2.62	170	0.955	2.71	300	1.114
6	Ad is relevant to product	3.32	130	1.321	2.69	170	1.112	2.97	300	1.246
7	Does it reflect company image	1.89	130	0.975	2.29	170	0.971	2.12	300	0.991
8	The claims made is believable	3.77	130	1.362	3.07	170	1.173	3.38	300	1.306

Correlations			
		Female Mean	Male Mean
Female Mean	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	8	8
Male Mean	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	8	8
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Resulted figures give the evidence that null hypothesis i.e. Gender and respondents’ opinion is not significantly correlated, is rejected as the ‘P’ value is 0.000 at 0.01 alpha level at two tailed. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is Gender and respondents’ opinions are significantly correlated. It means there is no gender difference in the opinion of respondents towards the advertisement of Faire and Lovely.

H 02: Gender and respondent’ perception towards the product features’ importance are not significantly correlated

Case Summary

Sr.	Product Features	Male			Female			Total		
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
1	Fairness	2.89	130	1.399	2.43	170	1.277	2.63	300	1.351
2	Dark Spots	2.92	130	1.496	2.20	170	1.223	2.52	300	1.396
3	Pimples	2.67	130	1.507	2.15	170	1.278	2.38	300	1.405
4	Under Eye treatment	3.17	130	1.458	2.33	170	1.315	2.70	300	1.439
5	Skin Dullness	2.73	130	1.488	2.32	170	1.291	2.50	300	1.394

Correlations			
		Mean of male	Mean of female
Mean of male	Pearson Correlation	1	1.000**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	5	5
Mean of female	Pearson Correlation	1.000**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Results shows that null hypotheses i.e. Gender and respondent’ perception towards the product features’ importance are not significantly correlated, is rejected as the ‘P’ value is 0.000 at two tailed with alpha level 0.01. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is selected that gender and perception towards the importance of features of product is significantly correlated. It means there is no gender difference into the perception of respondents regarding importance of product (Fair and Lovely) features.

Limitations and Scope for future work

The responses collected during 2014-15, responses were nothing but the perception of students, and it may change in future. The result which is obtained in selected area Satara, may not generalize to other areas and with other customers as sample selected were students.

There is future scope to investigate brand awareness and their brand perception towards the Fair and Lovely, factors influence the positive perception, advertising clutter impact and to check a brand endorsement influence on purchase intention. Also scope to work on to compare the ad impact of Fair and Lovely with other school-going students.

Conclusion

The advertisements of Fair & Lovely have changed from time to time since its launching. Where young generation presented in both genders. However, females are more preferred of Fair and Lovely than males. The result of collected data reveals that there is no gender difference regarding the

ad message and perception towards the importance of features of the product. It indicates the marketing efforts of Fair and Lovely, ad message is successful in creating the right perception among the respondents, and there was no scope left for perceptual distortion about this fairness cream. Therefore, researcher finds scope to sell this product to all and not to a specific female segment. Since the male is also now becoming look caution that emerges male parlor in Satara.

Managerial Implications

Fairness is considered as a part of Personality Development by young generation irrespective of gender, nature of qualification. Ad influences buyer but the frequency of watching of the ad makes the difference in making of positive perception. Therefore, the marketer needs to take effort in holding the attention of viewers and make them watch more frequently. The content of the ad should match the target customer and environment of ad presentation should suit to the current young generation. Therefore, there is a need to change the punch line 'Sirf cream nahi, fairness treatment hai', should highlight on graceful, smart look and enrich personality also which can match to the current young generation as today's young generation is more rational, conscious about health and personality, does not like to spend much and not dreamy they need solution to overcome their problem. So make the sachet available similar like a shampoo price as one-time use and allow the customer for the experience.

Annexure: 1

Table 1 Sample Distribution as per Gender

Gender	Frq	%
Female	170	56.67
Male	130	43.33
Total	300	100.00

Table 2 Sample Distribution as per Age

Sr.	Age Group	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Below 25	129	99.23	166	97.65	295.00	98.33
2	25-35	1	0.77	4	2.35	5.00	1.67
Total		130	100	170	100	300	100

Table 3 Frequency to seen ad on Television in a week

Sr.	Times	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Once	4	3.08	4	2.35	8	2.67
2	Two	10	7.69	22	12.94	32	10.67
3	Three	22	16.92	24	14.12	46	15.33
4	Four	30	23.08	48	28.24	78	26.00
5	Five Plus	64	49.23	72	42.35	136	45.33
Total		130	100.00	170	100.00	300	100.00

No single customer found that he has nver seen the ad

Table 4 Opinion on Advt Appeal

Sr.	Opinion	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Yes	102	78.46	128	75.29	230	76.67
2	No	28	21.54	42	24.71	70	23.33
Total		130	100.00	170	100	300	100.00

Table 5 Positive Reaction towards advertisement

Sr.	Opinion	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Yes	96	73.85	144	84.71	240	80
2	No	34	26.15	26	15.29	60	20
Total		130	100.00	170	100.00	300	100

Table 6 Sample Customer Like to See the ad in Future

Sr.	Opinion	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Yes	90	69.23	130	76.47	220	73.33
2	NO	40	30.77	40	23.53	80	26.67
Total		130	100.00	170	100.00	300	100.00

Table 7 Sample Customer More Likely to Purchase offered Product

Sr.	Opinion	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Yes	86	66.15	130	76.47	216	72
2	No	44	33.85	40	23.53	84	28
Total		130	100.00	170	100.00	300	100

Table 8 Sample Customer Like to Share ad to Someone

Sr.	Opinion	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Yes	62	47.69	112	65.88	174	58
2	No	68	52.31	58	34.12	126	42
Total		130	100.00	170	100.00	300	100

Table 9 Opinion of Sample on Fair & Lovely Ad

Sr.	Statement	Female		Male		Total	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
1	Is it creative	2.40	0.99	2.41	0.99	2.40	0.99
2	Is it informative	2.56	1.14	2.57	1.14	2.56	1.14
3	Is it memorable	2.59	1.25	2.60	1.25	2.59	1.25
4	Is it original	2.62	1.16	2.63	1.16	2.62	1.16
5	Is it influential	2.70	1.11	2.71	1.11	2.70	1.11
6	Is it relevant to product	2.96	1.24	2.97	1.24	2.96	1.24
7	Does it reflect company image	2.11	0.99	2.11	0.99	2.11	0.99
8	The claims made is believable	3.36	1.31	3.37	1.30	3.36	1.31

Table 10 Samples Opinion on ad message

Sr.	Opinion	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	Just trying to sell the product	60	46.15	56	32.94	116	38.67
2	Product is of high quality	20	15.38	18	10.59	38	12.67
3	Entice people to try the product	0	0.00	56	32.94	56	18.67
4	Cheaper than the competitors	16	12.31	6	3.53	22	7.33
5	Brand awareness, company trying to expose itself	20	15.38	26	15.29	46	15.33
6	Other	14	10.77	8	4.71	22	7.33
Total		130	100.00	170	100.00	300	100.00

Table 11 Sample's Television Watching Frequency in a Day

Sr.	Watching Frequency	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
1	None	12	9.23	6	3.53	18	6
2	Less than 1 hour	52	40.00	72	42.35	124	41.33
3	1-2 hours	50	38.46	52	30.59	102	34.00
4	3-4 hours	4	3.08	24	14.12	28	9.33
5	More than 4 hours	12	9.23	16	9.41	28	9.33
Total		130	100.00	170	100.00	300	100

Table 12 Sample Opinion on Importance of Product Features

Sr.	Product Features	Male		Female		Total	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Fairness	2.63	1.35	2.63	1.35	2.63	1.35
2	Dark Spots	2.51	1.39	2.51	1.39	2.51	1.40
3	Pimples	2.37	1.40	2.37	1.40	2.37	1.41
4	Under treatment Eye	2.69	1.44	2.69	1.44	2.69	1.44
5	Skin Dullness	2.50	1.39	2.50	1.39	2.50	1.39

Table 13 Perception of Samples towards Fair & Lovely ad

Sr.	Opinion	Male	Female	Total
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No.		Frequency	%	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
1	Memorable	44	33.85	20	11.76	64	21.33
2	Emotional	20	15.38	4	2.35	24	8.00
3	Creative	52	40.00	44	25.88	96	32.00
4	Attention Getting	24	18.46	30	17.65	54	18.00
5	Genuine	24	18.46	10	5.88	34	11.33
6	Unique	48	36.92	24	14.12	62	20.67
7	Cheerful	32	24.62	32	18.82	64	21.33
8	Informative	22	16.92	26	15.29	48	16.00
9	Boring	30	23.08	20	11.76	50	16.67
10	Satisfying	30	23.08	36	21.18	66	22.00
11	Offensive	16	12.31	0	0.00	16	5.33
12	Natural	30	23.08	34	20.00	64	21.33
13	Energetic	22	16.92	12	7.06	34	11.33
14	Honest	28	21.54	16	9.41	44	14.67
15	Pleasant	22	16.92	24	14.12	46	15.33
16	Irritating	22	16.92	4	2.35	26	8.67
17	Other	28	21.54	6	3.53	34	11.33

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